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Potential Hydrodynamic Effects and Power Production Impacts of Submerged Debris on a Marine Hydrokinetic Turbine

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Abstract

Natural vegetation in a riverine environment can create the potential for hazardous debris due to the dynamic nature of evolving fluvial environments. For instance, as channel planforms evolve through lateral migration, forces in riverine flows will erode channel banks causing bankline trees to fall into the flow and become floating debris. Such debris can often be observed to accumulate during flood flows on manmade structures located in the river such as at bridge piers. Similarly, marine hydrokinetic turbine (MHK) installations within a riverine environment will create barriers to floating and submerged debris and can be expected to experience debris piles collecting on their towers. Using Large-Eddy Simulations (LESs), this study has evaluated six different levels of debris loads lodged at the base of the tower of a horizontal-axis turbine. The flow around the turbine was modeled using an actuator line model. The hydrodynamic effects of all simulations were analyzed demonstrating that increasing the size of the debris accumulations causes more flow to bypass the lower regions of the MHK, thereby reducing the time-averaged flow velocity magnitude reaching the MHK blades at the lower depths leading to appreciable reductions in the average power produced by the MHK. Furthermore, turbulent shedding behind the larger debris piles produced greater vorticity and turbulent fluctuations in the flow in the upper regions of the MHK leading to greater variability in the power production.

Keywords: vegetation; debris; turbine; MHK; LES; Actuator Models

1. Background

Natural vegetation in a riverine environment can create the potential for hazardous debris due to the dynamic nature of evolving fluvial environments. For instance, as channel planforms evolve through lateral migration, forces in riverine flows will erode channel banks causing bank line trees to fall into the flow and become floating debris. Such debris can often be observed to accumulate during flood flows on manmade structures located in the river such as at bridge piers. Similarly, the MHK turbines, installed in waterways, can encounter floating debris potentially leading to accumulation of debris piles on their towers. Debris typically moves during flood flow events and deposits during the recession limb of the flood hydrograph. Often floating debris is transported as individual logs and is transported along the thalweg of the stream [1, 2, 3].

However, the debris-flow-MHK turbine interaction is highly complex and thus difficult to study in natural settings [7]. To address this issue, high-fidelity modeling on massively parallel computing clusters can provide insight into the intricate interaction and understand the potential impacts of debris on power production of MHKs.

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2. Objective

This study performs systematical analysis to show how debris accumulations might impact the hydrodynamics and power production of a horizontal-axis MHK turbine by using large eddy simulations (LESs). By comparing the flow and power generation of a baseline MHK case free of any debris to six different cases of debris configurations of increasing debris density, estimates of the loss of power production and reduction in the power efficiency were determined.

3. Methodology

For this study, an advanced turbulence modeling technique, the large eddy simulation (LES), is used because it is capable of capturing a wide range of turbulent eddy sizes and resolve the instantaneous flow around the debris accumulations and MHK. Such high-fidelity simulations, however, incur a high computational cost. Hence, incorporating mid-fidelity solutions for the rotating model such as an actuator line model with high-fidelity modeling can help to economize the computational costs while predicting precise results for the flow field [4].

On the other hand, debris are regarded as immersed bodies integrated into the riverine environment, allowing their profound effects to directly engage with the flow and the MHK turbine. The approach of debris-resolving method is essential for addressing turbulence fluctuations and vorticity, which give rise to hydrodynamic influences and power generation [5].

To accurately replicate real-world conditions, varying-sized debris piles are randomly located for six different debris configurations (Figure 1). For the baseline scenario (Case 0), the debris pile was ignored by focusing solely on observing flow-MHK turbine interactions. The number of logs in debris piles and the frontal area (i.e., the surface area perpendicular to the streamwise flow) for each case are outlined in Table 1. For each successive case, new logs are incorporated into the existing accumulation leaving the previous cases logs in their original positions.

Figure 1: Illustration showing the debris accumulations for the six cases studied. The red logs indicate the additional logs which were added to the previous case accumulation shown in black.

Table 1: Debris Parameters for Cases Simulated

Case	0	1	2	3	4	5	6
Number of Logs in Pile	0	2	3	5	8	10	12
Frontal Area (m ²)	0	0.473	0.565	0.672	0.886	1.027	1.156

In this systematic study, a horizontal-axis MHK with a rotor diameter of 5 meters and tip speed ratio of 2.5 was simulated in a 25 m wide by 87.5 m long flume. The depth of flow simulated was 7.8 m with a free stream velocity of 1.56 m/s. The system is non-dementalized based on the rotor diameter and 18.9 million grid nodes with a uniform spacing in all directions of 0.02 m are utilized in the numerical model. Utilizing the actuator line model to capture the effect of the blades on the flow, the turbine blades are represented as a line. Each blade of the rotor is modeled with a straight line, divided into 101 elements along the radial direction. In each of the elements, drag and lift forces are computed. This is achieved by utilizing tabulated airfoil data which includes the drag-lift coefficient variations with respect to angle of attacks and chord length and twist angle of the original airfoil. In particular, the drag and lift coefficients play an important role in computing the distributed forces over the line. This model functions as a momentum sink, creating flow along rotating lines that correspond to each individual rotor blade. [6]

4. Results

Figure 2 compares the number of revolution history of power production of the MHK turbine, employing the actuator line model. The turbine requires approximately four seconds to complete one full cycle. After five revolutions, a consistent power production pattern is observed for each case, prompting a systematic analysis of up to five revolutions. The scenario referred to as Case-0, represented by a solid red line, pertains to instances where only the interaction between the flow and the MHK turbine is considered since no debris is on the MHK. In this case, aside from the turbine tower leading to turbulent wake regions, there are no obstacles causing turbulent fluctuations in the flow, resulting in a rapid convergence of power production at around 0.5 s. The fluctuations in the power produced for Case-0 are caused when one of the blades is in the lower region of the MHK passes in the wake of the MHK tower, but the other two blades are placed in the upper region of the MHK turbine. The amplitude of these fluctuations is relatively small (approximately 1.1 kW).

Figure 2: Time-series of the power production using the actuator Line Model for the baseline case (0) shown in Red and the six debris cases (1-6).

The MHK turbine power outputs are also computed for the six cases with debris, Figure 2 demonstrates an appreciable decrease in power production for successively larger debris piles and also a much larger variability in temporal output represented by a large range from crest to trough in the power. Because turbulent shedding behind the larger debris piles produced greater vorticity and turbulent fluctuations in the flow in the upper regions of the MHK, thereby the turbulent fluctuations altered the temporal stability of the power production. These effects on average power production and variability are summarized in Table 2 and shown in Figure 4. Figure 3(a) depicts the illustration of the turbulent structure near the debris and turbine.

Figure 3: (a) Instantaneous turbulent flow structures being shed from around the debris accumulations as shown by the Q criterion value of 20 and (b) the change in velocity magnitude from the upstream freestream velocity (1.56 m/s) caused by the wake of the debris accumulation.

Table 2: Results of Power Production and Power Efficiency for Cases Simulated

Case	0	1	2	3	4	5	6
Average Power (kW)	9.69	8.24	8.12	7.95	6.71	6.37	6.45
Average Power Amplitude (kW)	1.15	2.47	2.73	2.64	3.04	3.52	2.86
Average Power Coefficient, C_p	0.259	0.221	0.218	0.213	0.179	0.171	0.173

Additionally, the study revealed that the turbine efficiency changes with debris impacts. Increasing the size of the debris accumulations causing more flow to bypass the upper regions of the MHK, thereby reducing in the time-averaged flow velocity magnitude reaching the MHK blades at the lower depths (Figure 3(b)). The flow bypassing the lower region of the MHK can be related to the frontal area of debris in streamwise direction. When the frontal area is increased with additional logs, a significant decrease in turbine efficiency calculated as the power coefficient, C_p , from

$$C_p = \frac{2P}{\rho A U_\infty^3}$$

where P is the power produced by the turbine, ρ is the density of water, A is the area blocked by the rotating rotors and U_∞ is the upstream free stream velocity. The values for C_p for each case are shown in Table 2.

Figure 4: Plot of power production (red) and average variation between peak power production and minimum production per revolution (green line) for different amounts of frontal area of debris blockage for all cases.

5. Conclusions

Debris accumulations at MHK turbines have been shown in the LESs to significantly reduce the efficiency of its operation and produce lower power. These effects appear to be strongly correlated to the amount of upstream blockage of the flow as reflected by the projected frontal area and are understood to be caused from a loss in momentum in the flow behind the debris and an increase in turbulent structures shed from the debris.

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